

Recommendations and a possible solution to prevent authors
from paying to publish in journals.

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Abstract

Paying to publish in journals has raised the accountability of what is being done with the paid money. This short communication deals with a recommendation and a possible solution for authors from sciences and social sciences to avoid payment to publish in journals.

Key words: scientists, payment, journals, accountability , tax relief

Lines from two references published in mainstream media are cited below to justify the recommendation and a possible solution. The first reference has the following lines. "The way to make money from a scientific article looks very similar, except that scientific publishers manage to duck most of the actual costs. Scientists create work under their own direction – funded largely by governments – and give it to publishers for **free**; the publisher pays scientific editors who judge whether the work is worth publishing and check its grammar, but the bulk of the editorial burden – checking the scientific validity and evaluating the experiments, a process known as peer review – is done by working scientists on a volunteer basis. The publishers then sell the product back to government-funded institutional and university libraries, to be read by scientists – who, in a collective sense, created the product in the first place" (Buranyi 2017)

The second reference has lines attributed to Dr. Elizabeth Bik, a pioneering science integrity specialist and recent winner of the John Maddox Prize. The lines are as follows "We [scientists] write the papers for free, we peer-review them for free, and then still we have to pay **the publisher \$4,000 to get our paper published,**" she said. "Where does that money go to? It seems a lot of people sitting in shiny offices, bosses of bosses of bosses, people who don't seem to be doing something directly to my paper. It's hard to justify." (Hannah 2021)

Recommendations.

The first reference states, “The publishers then sell the product back to government-funded institutional and university libraries, to be read by scientists”(Buranyi 2017). Now government-funded institutes pay an annual subscription to the publishing houses. Most of the universities audit their accounts and are transparent about their annual payment. The second reference says, “ scientists pay \$ 4000 to get our paper published. Then there is a statement, “ Where does the money go to ?” In effect, Dr. Bik is inferring to an audit. If this is the case, then publishing houses must be transparent and declare where the money is going in the last annual issue of the journal or on their website. The transparency exhibited by government-funded universities for the annual subscription paid to the publishers for their online libraries is a good example for publishers to emulate.

Possible solution

Let us assume a university publishes ten papers in a prestigious journal that charges \$4,000 per paper. The total comes to \$40 000. If twenty-five universities from a country publish ten articles each from different university departments in this prestigious journal, the total payment comes to a million dollars. The million-dollar guesstimate goes for salaries and benefits for a specified number of 'scientific editors of' this prestigious journal. The irony of this publishing game is the hard work done by scientists who perform, write a paper, be an unpaid peer reviewer and then pay to publish with the money of an unknown taxpayer. Some of the unidentified taxpayers in countries with "not so rich, poorly funded universities "may be struggling to make both ends meet.

It is proposed to impose a 15 % tax on Big Tech companies (Rappeport 2021). Big Tech companies whose technology platforms the prestigious journals use can pay the salaries and benefits to the 'scientific editors' and other expenses. They can get tax relief on a dollar-to-dollar basis on the proposed 15% tax. Publishers should talk to the Big Tech companies about this tax relief proposal and not make authors pay to publish. Audit transparency and this proposed tax relief would divert funds for paying increased scholarships to doctoral students who form the pinnacle of intellectual repository of a university. .

Disclosure statement: No potential conflict interest of statement reported by the author

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